

Surgical Site Infections and Affiliated Factors in Individuals Taking General Surgeries

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To determine contributing factors towards development of surgical site infections in patients taking general surgeries.

Materials and Methods: The study included patients with surgical site infections, developed after undergoing general surgeries. The information such as obesity, surgical duration, hospital stay duration, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, smoking and number of blood transfusions was noted.

Results: The study included 80 patients with age more than 18 years. About 52% of patients had age range of 45 to 60 years, whereas, 15% were above 60 years. The remaining cases belonged to age ranges of 18-30 and 31-45 years. The study included 57 (71.25%) males and 33 (41.25%) females. The factors responsible for causing surgical site infection were smoking (20.1%), multiple blood transfusions (14.2%), obesity (14.2%), and prolonged hospital stay (16.2%). Hypertension was present in 11.1% patients and diabetes was prevalent in 12.4% patients. Other 11.8% cases belonged to unknown causes.

Conclusion: The contributing factors found associated with development of surgical site infection included multiple blood transfusions, prolonged hospital stay, smoking, obesity, and emergency surgery.

Key Words: General Surgery, Surgical site infection, SSI

INTRODUCTION

The infection of surgical site may take place at surgically operated area after a surgery. Surgical site infection (SSI) is usually accidental in nature and can be prevented. It has been associated with increased morbidity and costliness of healthcare (Bibi et al. 2011). The occurrence of SSI varies from hospital to hospital all over the world. The rate of SSI is reported to be 2.50% to 41.90% in literature. According to an estimate SSI occur in 2% of surgeries, which makes about 1,400,000 cases. SSI may have different severity depending upon the case (Alfonso-Sanchez et al. 2017). It is considered as most common complication as well as nosocomial infection. It comprises of 20% of

healthcare related infections and 38% of nosocomial infections following surgeries. A previous research work documented that 13% of patients undergoing surgery developed SSIs in Pakistan (Jenks et al. 2014).

Various research works have been conducted to elaborate SSI and to understand different risk factors contributing towards their occurrence. Moreover, research has also been conducted to devise ways for controlling these factors at clinical level (Taylor, Gosman & Kelley 2017). Consequently, different research works have indicated different risk factors to be responsible for SSI. Some studies have pointed out towards transfusion to be a significant risk factor for development of SSI (Shah, Singh & Rathod 2017). Other factors indicated by previous studies include increasing age, diabetes mellitus, preoperative hospital stay, ASA score more than 3, emergency surgery, contaminated surgical sites and extended duration of surgical procedure. However, a recent systemic review has claimed that there is lack of data in Pakistan regarding post operative wound infections (Tariq et al. 2017). With tremendous increase in SSI over previous few years, it is important to determine its prevalence and responsible factors. However, World Health Organization (WHO) has claimed that majority of underdeveloped countries has no adequate data with regard to SSI. To implement preventative measures against SSI, its risk factors need to be identified (Michael 2017). Thus, the present study aims to determine responsible factors for SSI in individuals undergoing general surgeries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research work was conducted at Surgery Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore from June 2017 to June 2018. This cross sectional study included patients with surgical site infections, developed after general surgeries. The patients with age more than 18 years were included which belonged to both the genders. The patients who were not willing to participate in study were not

included. Moreover, patients with diagnosis of malignancy and tuberculosis were also excluded. Classification of wound infection was done on the basis of surgical site infection. The information such as diabetes mellitus, obesity, prolonged surgical duration, hospital stay, smoking, number of blood transfusions and hypertension were noted. The collected data was analyzed through SPSS v.17.

RESULTS

The study included 80 cases of surgical site infection. About 52% of patients had age range of 45 to 60 years, whereas, 15% were above 60 years. The remaining cases belonged to age ranges of 18-30 and 31-45 years. The study included 57 (71.25%) males and 33 (41.25%) females. The factors responsible for causing surgical site infection were smoking (20.1%), multiple blood transfusions (14.2%), obesity (14.2%), and prolonged hospital stay (16.2%). Hypertension was present in 11.1% patients and diabetes was prevalent in 12.4% patients. Other 11.8% cases belonged to unknown causes.

DISCUSSION

Majority of the patients included in this study had age more than 45 years. According to Neumayer et al (2007), age is an independent risk factor for SSI development. Same was found in present study, where patients with age more than 45 years had significant raised risk of developing SSI. Many cases (71%) undergoing emergency surgery were related with development of SSI. Sanabria et al (2014) found similar results. Obesity was responsible for development of SSI in 14.2% patients. Obesity was indicated as an important risk factor for SSI by research work conducted by Rasul et al (2016). The reason can be poor vascularization of adipose tissue, which results in oxygenation of tissues leading to increased risk of SSI. Consequently, obese patients may have longer and more complex surgeries.

The smokers have reduced progress in wound healing, which is effected by reduced oxygen

carrying ability and vasoconstrictive effects of blood. In present study, 20.1% patients developed SSI due to smoking. In a study conducted by Graante et al (2008), smokers were found to develop SSI significantly as compared to non-smokers. Consequently, smokers who smoked more cigarettes had additional chances of developing SSI.

Many previous research works have indicated that hyperglycemia is highly linked with perioperative complications. In present study, SSI was developed in 12.4% diabetic patients. Ata et al (2010) emphasized that postoperative hyperglycemia is an important factor in causing SSI. Similarly, Bibi et al (2011) claimed that diabetic patients have 3.6 times more risk of developing SSI as compared to non-diabetics.

In present study, 14.2% patients developed SSI due to multiple blood transfusions. However, study of Micheal et al (2017) claimed that blood transfusion is related with development of SSI. It may be linked with organ space and septic shock SSI, developed after colon resection. Although transfusion is a lifesaving intervention, it is linked with many complications including infection.

In present study, 16.2% individuals with prolonged hospital stay developed SSI. The work of Malik et al (2015) indicated that individuals with SSIs have high variance in terms of hospital stay as compared to non-SSI individuals. The prolonged hospital stay due to SSI is the main reason for increasing affiliated cost. The work of Florio et al (2006) has also claimed that obesity, prolonged preoperative stay, AIDS and diabetes are contributing factors towards SSI.

CONCLUSION

The risk factors found highly associated with development of surgical site infection included prolonged hospital stay, smoking, obesity, emergency surgery and multiple blood transfusions. Surgeons should be cognizant about development of infection in patients with these respective factors.

REFERENCES

- Alfonso-Sanchez, J, Martinez, I, Martín-Moreno, J, González, R & Botía, F 2017, 'Analyzing the risk factors influencing surgical site infections: the site of environmental factors', *Canadian J Surg*, vol 60, no. 3, p. 155.
- Ansar, A 2013, 'Surgical Site Infection in Obstetrics Practice', *J Surg Pak*, vol 18, no. 2.
- Ata, A, Lee, J, Bestle, S, Desemone, J & Stain, S 2010, 'Postoperative hyperglycemia and surgical site infection in general surgery patients', *Archives of Surg*, vol 145, no. 9, pp. 858-64.

- Bibi, S, Channa, G, Siddiqui, T & Ahmed, W 2011, 'Frequency and risk factors of surgical site infections in general surgery ward of a tertiary care hospital of Karachi, Pakistan', *Int J Infect Control*, vol 7, no. 3, p. 5.
- Bruce, J, Russell, E & Mollison, J 2001, 'The quality of measurement of surgical wound infection as the basis for monitoring: a systematic review', *J Hosp Infect*, vol 49, pp. 99-108.
- Burnett, J, Gustilo, R, Williams, D & Kind, A 1980, 'Prophylactic antibiotic in hip fractures: a double— blind prospective study', *J Bone Joint Surg Am*, vol 62, pp. 457–462.
- de Lissovoy, G, Fraeman, K, Hutchins, V, Murphy, D, Song, D & Vaughn, B 2009, 'Surgical site infection: incidence and impact on hospital utilization and treatment costs', *Am J Infect Control*, vol 37, pp. 387–397.
- Fiorio, M, Marvaso, A, Viganò, F & Marchetti, F 2006, 'Incidence of surgical site infections in general surgery in Italy', *Infect*, vol 34, no. 6, p. 310.
- Gravante, G, Araco, A & Sorge, R 2008, 'Postoperative wound infections after breast reductions: The role of smoking and the amount of tissue removed', *Aesthetic Plastic Surg*, vol 32, pp. 25– 31.
- Jenks, P, Laurent, M, Mcquarry, S & Watkins, R 2014, 'Clinical and economic burden of surgical site infection (SSI) and predicted financial consequences of elimination of SSI from an English hospital', *J Hospital Infec*, vol 86, pp. 24-29.
- Khan, M, Rehman, S, Ali, M, Sultan, B & Sultan, S 2008, 'Infection in Orthopedic Implant Surgery, Its Risk Factors and Outcome', *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*, vol 20, no. 1, pp. 23-5.
- Malik, A 2015, 'Surgical Site Infections after Elective Surgery in Pakistan: SURGIPAK Study', *J Rawalpindi Med Coll*, vol 19, no. 3, pp. 209-14.
- Michael, M 2017, 'Red Blood Cell Transfusion and Surgical Site Infection After Colon Resection Surgery: A Cohort Study.', *Anesthesia and analgesia*, vol 125, no. 4.
- Neumayer, L, Hosokawa, P & Itani, K 2007, 'Multivariable predictors of postoperative surgical site infection after general and vascular surgery: results from the patient safety in surgery study', *J Am Coll Surgeons*, vol 204, pp. 1178–87.
- Nichols, R 2004, 'Preventing surgical site infections', *Clin Med Res*, vol 2, no. 2, pp. 115-8.
- Noordzij, P, Boersma, E & Schreiner, F 2007, 'Increased preoperative glucose levels are associated with perioperative mortality in patients undergoing noncardiac, nonvascular surgery', *Eur J Endocrinol*, vol 156, pp. 137–142.
- Olsen, M, Mayfield, J & Laurysen, C 2003, 'Risk factors for surgical site infection in spinal surgery', *J Neurosurg*, vol 98, pp. 149–55.
- Pear, S 2007, 'Patient risk factors and best practices for surgical site infection prevention', *Managing Infection Control*, pp. 56-64.
- Rasul, A, Muhammad, Y, Gondal, K, Siddique, H & Karn, A 2016, 'Prevalence of Obesity in Surgical Patients Undergoing Abdominal Surgery at Mayo Hospital Lahore Pakistan', *Pak J Med Health Sci*, vol 10, no. 3, pp. 713-5.
- Sanabria, A, Vega, V, Dominguez, L, Espitia, E, Serna, A & Osorio, C 2014, 'The evolution of laparoscopy in abdominal surgery: a meta-analysis of the effect on infectious outcomes', *Minimally Invasive Therapy & Allied Technologies*, vol 23, no. 2, pp. 74-86.
- Sangrasi, A 2008, 'Surgical site infection rate and associated risk factors in elective general surgery at a public sector medical university in Pakistan', *Int Wound J*, vol 5, no. 1, pp. 74-78.
- Shah, K, Singh, S & Rathod, J 2017, 'Surgical site infections: incidence, bacteriological profiles and risk factors in a tertiary care teaching hospital, western India', *Int J Med Sci Publ Health*, vol 6, no. 1, pp. 173-7.
- Tariq, A, Ali, H, Zafar, F, Sial, A & Hameed, K 2017, 'A Systemic Review on Surgical Site Infections: Classification, Risk Factors, Treatment Complexities, Economical and Clinical Scenarios', *J Bioequiv Availab*, vol 9, pp. 336-40.
- Taylor, AE, Gosman, GG & Kelley, JL 2017, 'An Assessment of Risk Factors for Surgical Site Infection and Superficial Wound Separation in Gynecologic Oncology Patients', *Women's Health & Gynecol*, vol 2, no. 1, pp. 2-5.
- Weber, W, Zwahlen, M & Reck, S 2009, 'The association of preoperative anemia and perioperative allogeneic blood transfusion with the risk of surgical site infection', *Transfusion*, vol 49, no. 9, pp. 1964-1970.